

Fact Sheet

Building capacity for resilient and inclusive conservation of cultural landscapes

Methodological guide - a primer

By Erik Andersson, My Sellberg, Jan J. Kuiper
Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden

Introduction

This paper presents a collaborative approach to building a collective capacity to identify, evaluate, combine and adapt multiple coexisting strategies for resilient and inclusive conservation of cultural landscapes, exemplified by a pilot application in the mosaic landscape of Östergötland, Sweden. The paper is intended for planners, policy makers and other actors who seek to maintain and develop mixed multifunctional landscapes in a rapidly changing world. The work presented in this paper will be further developed over the course of the ENVISION project based on continued stakeholder engagement.

ENVISION is a transdisciplinary research project that develops an inclusive approach to the management of protected areas, known as inclusive conservation, with the aim of improving biodiversity and human well-being. A cornerstone of inclusive conservation is the application of multiple methods that function to expand the space for engagement and dialogue across the various stakeholders of a protected area, such as recreational users, local residents, local businesses, land managers, farmers, researchers and local governments. ENVISION investigates inclusive approaches in protected areas in the United States (Denali National Park, Alaska), Spain (Sierra de Guadarrama National Park), the Netherlands (Kromme Rijn and Utrechtse Heuvelrug National Park) and Sweden (Västra Hargs Lövängar Nature Reserve in Östergötland).

“Inclusive conservation” is an approach for accommodating and balancing different visions for protected area management and for achieving socially relevant, economically viable, and environmentally sustainable outcomes in protected areas. The approach considers multiple visions for how nature should be conserved, assessing the consequences of each vision, collectively defining new visions through social learning, assessing uncertainty and building resilience, acknowledging power relations and rethinking governance.

Inclusive conservation in cultural landscapes

The United Nations declared “a decade of action” to meet the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030. Taking a step further, the Global Assessment of the Intergovernmental Science Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)¹ and the 5th Global Biodiversity Outlook of the Convention on Biological Diversity² call for “transformative” action to achieve the vision on biodiversity agreed by world governments for 2050 ‘Living in Harmony with Nature’. While the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework of the CBD is still under negotiation it is evident that the world will have to step up the efforts with conserving biodiversity and protecting nature. Already, the new EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 calls for “at least 30% of the land and 30% of the sea to be protected in the European Union”³. In many regions, however, conservation goals need to be met in landscapes populated by people and thus replete with different ownership patterns, governance models and land uses including forestry and agriculture. Inclusivity, therefore, is a key enabling condition required for the achievement of ambitious conservation targets.

Common to all human inhabited landscapes is that human management is an integral part of conservation. In traditional cultural landscapes – like woodland pastures, semi-natural grasslands and small scale, low intensity crop production and forestry – species and habitats have evolved together with cultural management systems, resulting in significant ecological, biological, cultural and scenic values. The target of 30% area designated as protected areas will need to include a considerable share of cultural landscapes, and here formal protection may not in itself suffice to guarantee successful biodiversity conservation. Maintaining and restoring the integrity of people-nature interactions is vital to protecting and sustaining the area and its associated conservation values. This includes promoting the sustainable use of natural resources and protecting ecosystems services to enhance social and economic benefits to local communities, as a means to achieving nature conservation.

Positioning protected areas as embedded in and connected to the larger landscape also means extending the conservation efforts beyond protected area boundaries, acknowledging the diverse interactions between protected areas and adjacent land uses. Less intensive land use and diversified production systems offer many ways to ease the tension between production and conservation. Many production landscapes have a long history as cultural landscapes, even though the last 100 years has seen industrialized production landscapes push back older, often less intensively used cultural landscapes. But legacies of less intensive use remain, such as interstitial grass margins, forest edges, streams, hedges and stone fences that hold a diversity of species, patches of land where traditional management is upheld, and cultural activities including craft fairs and farmer markets. These offer seeds for ideas and opportunities to expand conservation work also into production landscapes and tap into the potential for collective, potentially transformative action. A unifying challenge for protected area management is the need to engage with local values, interests and visions, as well as policies, initiatives and collaborative processes that are already in place, to broaden the stewardship of landscapes and the natural and cultural heritage that they contain.

Toward resilient and inclusive conservation of cultural landscapes

In mixed landscapes defined by coexisting land uses, landscape quality is an outcome of a confluence of actions by local actors with diverse, ever-changing and potentially conflicting needs, interests and desires. This poses a challenge for management, which is even more pronounced in times of unprecedented societal and environmental changes, when management strategies need not only to deal with the current situation but also be flexible and resilient enough to navigate novel circumstances such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

One of the objectives within ENVISION is to identify and actively work with uncertainties and interdependencies in multi-stakeholder efforts to govern and move a landscape towards collectively defined visions. Based on research on social-ecological systems we position *resilience, or the capacity to absorb disturbance, reorganize and retain essentially the same functions over time*⁴, as a central feature for making sure that desired qualities of the landscape are maintained despite different pressures and ongoing changes. Resilience may involve adaptation or even transformation to a different kind of system in addition to robustness. There are many alternative ways for how to work with resilience principles including the Wayfinder guide⁵, the 7 resilience principles⁶ and Resilience Assessment Workbook⁷.

We draw on the Wayfinder guide as well as recent developments in resilience thinking on *pathway diversity*⁸ to introduce an approach for *building capacity among system actors to navigate changes and move the system toward a common vision*.

The approach we present focuses on how multiple parallel land-use and management strategies may coexist, complement or replace each other and hence shape the option space available to actors engaged in landscape governance. Our approach thus has the double objective of helping stakeholders identify and understand individual and collective strategies for managing and using a cultural landscape over time (including awareness of alternative options and interdependencies), and empowering stakeholders to engage with and make use of these strategies to collaborate towards a shared vision and handle emergent challenges. The approach is designed to create a safe space for dialogue to widen perspectives and open up solution space to move the system in the right direction even if stakeholders do not fully agree on a common vision.

The collective deliberation process draws on different sources of knowledge, such as scientific, local, experiential, indigenous knowledge. Weaving these together, the process gradually builds an understanding of the landscape itself (system knowledge - ecological connections, historical and current land use, drivers of environmental and social change etc.), the stakeholders (target knowledge - values, preferences, priorities etc.) and how to effect change through governance (transformational knowledge - decision contexts, organizational mandates, regulations etc.). This joint exploration deepens the stakeholders' understanding of the problems, solutions and different perspectives related to a sustainable management of landscape. Our approach to capacity building uses a flexible design that balances remote and on-site participation and lays the foundation for a continued collaboration between different actors and interests.

Methodological design

We exemplify our capacity building approach, using pathway diversity, with practical experiences and insights from the Västtra Harg pilot case study (Box 1). The approach is adapted from a participatory resilience assessment, which typically builds on a series of workshops and meetings, to working primarily through online platforms. This makes it suitable for situations where physical gatherings of people are difficult to arrange. The approach is organized into four phases:

1. Inventory and process design,
2. Problem and target formulation, identifying strategy components,
3. Articulating and describing strategies, and
4. Connecting strategies (Figure 1).

Collectively identifying strategies and turning them into action will require a combination of system, target and transformational knowledge. The design is iterative and dependent on stakeholder involvement, which means that each step builds on the previous and most likely will need adjustments throughout the process to meet the needs of different stakeholders. The knowledge needs of some stakeholders may be so specific that a more targeted follow-up may be needed after the participatory approach we describe. In the following we describe the questions and methods that guided our steps, and use insights from the Västtra Harg pilot case study to highlight important take-home messages about the challenges and success factors for the practical application of the approach.

Figure 1: The four phases of the exemplified capacity building approach for collaboratively developing resilient strategies for inclusive conservation of cultural landscapes

Box 1: Västra Hargs Lövskogar nature reserve and its surrounding cultural landscape – Case study

Together with local actors, the ENVISION project team designed a pilot application in the case study area in Sweden. Västra Hargs Lövskogar nature reserve, and its surrounding mosaic landscape, present an excellent case study highlighting the importance of boundaries - in the biophysical landscape as well as in its governance and use - for landscape multifunctionality and the capacity to deal with changes. Over the course of millennia, the interacting forces of nature and people have shaped this area into a landscape mosaic with high natural and cultural heritage values. Västra Hargs Lövskogar nature reserve is a relatively small protected area that preserves ancient oak wood-pastures including a rich diversity of traditional grassland species⁹. The reserve is situated in the middle of a transition gradient from intensive agriculture to dense forests. The transitional landscape is made up by mosaics of oak woodlands, mixed forests and open fields defined by more or less conspicuous edges and boundaries that simultaneously separate and connect different parts of the landscape, interests and activities¹⁰. This diversity is a source both of great richness as well as of tensions and conflict between coexisting interests and values.

The inherently shared governance of the landscape, with many stakeholders and decentralized decision making, faces a number of correlated challenges: degradation of the oak woodlands lurks while old pastures face afforestation, climate change is increasing risks of droughts and wildfires, nuisance species such as the spruce bark beetle and wild boars give rise to arguments over management practices, while economic interests in forestry and agriculture diverge from recreational interests and long-term biodiversity conservation targets. A collaborative process can strengthen the capacity to deal with diverging interests, uncertainties and future needs.

A broad introduction of the case study area and an explanation of how the case study is embedded within the broader ENVISION project can be found in an additional fact sheet¹¹ and policy brief¹².

Developing and testing a predominantly web based participatory approach

Piloting and providing input to the approach described in the factsheet, the process in Västra Harg was exploratory and grew organically as we had to adapt to changing circumstances due to COVID-19 as well as stakeholder input into the process (Figure 2). What was originally planned as a series of workshops had to be redesigned to work primarily through digital tools and platforms. Although this was a response to the 2020 COVID-19 situation the outcome is informative for any situation where physical meetings are difficult. We started with a combination of desk studies and scoping interviews (face to face or remotely) with key stakeholders (identified in the desk study, by local project partners or by other interviewees). Based on the information from this first phase we created a two-step online questionnaire building on the principles of a Delphi process and identified a representative group of stakeholders/respondents. Survey part 1 identified key issues and challenges in the landscape and explored underlying causes (capturing and articulating system, target and transformative knowledge). Survey part 2 sought confirmation of the results from the first and began the exploration of potential strategies for dealing with problems and strengthening appreciated qualities. Focal points for generating input to the development of strategies were the actors involved, potential action points, barriers to action and outcomes of actions. This information fed into a series of stakeholder engagement activities through webinars and a workshop where participants discussed common goals and potential strategies based on the above mentioned focal points. We now continue the engagement process in the case study area to develop the collective understanding of how strategies interact and could work together as a dynamic, flexible 'inclusive landscape strategy' that will help to safeguard and enhance the values of nature and its benefits to people in the case study area.

Figure 2: Overview of the collaboratively designed process at the Västra Harg case study that informed the four phases of the exemplified capacity building approach as presented in the fact sheet.

We summarized and synthesized the steps in our process into the four phases that are presented in this factsheet:

1. Inventory, and process design
2. Problem and target formulation, identifying strategy components
3. Articulating and describing strategies
4. Connecting strategies.

First phase: Inventory and process design

The first step is to define the system of interest, identify stakeholders and lay the foundations for the participatory process. Inclusive conservation is embedded in other issues like rural livability, property rights and land owner identities. More practically, the maintenance (or conservation) of cultural landscapes is often interwoven with food and timber production and constraints imposed by markets and various regulatory frameworks. The first phase includes: collecting baseline information, designing the process, and identifying the stakeholders who can help develop in-depth understanding of the case and who need to be involved in the participatory assessment. Stakeholders are people who on a professional or voluntary basis have a connection with and/or an impact on the landscape, on how it is understood and valued, or indirectly by being connected to any of the contextual factors (policy, education, outreach etc.). Gathered information helps to build a baseline understanding of the system across *system*, *target* and *transformative* knowledge. This includes information on ecological and sociocultural features of the landscape (e.g. status and trends of red listed species, land uses and land use history), who the stakeholders are and their values and interests, as well as policy background and context (e.g. statutory development plans, ongoing policy processes and initiatives).

- **Methods**

The first phase often consists of partner meetings to co-design the participatory process, scoping interviews with key informants and desktop studies of policies and plans, reports and scientific literature. Stakeholders can be identified from the gathering of information and initial system analysis, or by asking already identified local partners and participants about other actors that should be included. The inventory will produce many layers of information, which will need interpretation to inform understanding about what defines the context that embeds inclusive conservation. In this first phase, it is useful to concentrate on the elements, features and other factors that inform, or shape, the social-ecological character of the landscape.

- **Critical factors and reflection points**

This is the time to build alliances with key stakeholders and make sure the process is co-owned by stakeholders (degree can vary). Important questions are: *What are the main actors and important ongoing processes related to inclusive conservation in the case area?* and *How can they be involved in your process?*

Regarding the broader group of participants, the stakeholder mapping might rely heavily on existing networks and special care needs to be taken to invite stakeholders that are typically excluded from discussions about land use decisions and landscape qualities. An example may be an imbalanced gender representation among participating landowners in discussions about forestry.

The preliminary analysis and mapping primarily helps to articulate questions and an overarching framing for the next phase. Often, the scope of the process changes during this first, exploratory phase.

Second phase: Problem and target formulation, identifying strategy components

After having established what the system is in terms of central contextual factors, relevant policies and actors, i.e. what inclusive conservation would or could mean in the specific case, the next step is to define what the primary challenges and goals are and start to build an understanding of what could constitute tentative strategies for addressing these. This includes identifying who could take action to do different things (and to do things differently), what are the things that need to be done, what are the barriers to taking action and what might be the more far reaching consequences of taking action. Visions and goals are not 'set'; they will be continuously refined throughout the deliberation process. The barriers may include demographic, economic, organizational, technological or environmental changes and interdependencies. The different components - goals, actors, actions, barriers and impacts - make up the building blocks of different potentially coexisting strategies in the landscape (Figure 3).

- **Methods**

The second phase can for example be informed by an iterative online survey following the Delphi method, i.e. sending several rounds of questionnaires to a panel of stakeholders.

The anonymous responses are aggregated, analyzed and shared with the group after each round. The stakeholders are asked to adjust and expand on their answers in subsequent rounds, based on how they interpret the "group response" that has been provided to them. Since multiple rounds of questions are asked and the panel is told what the group thinks as a whole, the method seeks to find a comprehensive and (mostly) shared understanding of what the issues and possible solutions are. Tracking individual responses during several rounds shows the degree to which convergence occurs.

- **Critical factors and reflection points**

The second phase includes gathering data from a larger group of people in a more systematic way and serves to revise and deepen the initial systems analysis, and better understand the key issues that the process is framed around. Key issues are useful entry points to start entangling system dynamics - *What are useful entry points in your case and to whom?* This phase also asks the question of *what is already known about the system by the stakeholders and what are uncertainties according to the stakeholders?* Complementary activities, like open ended interviews or discussions with a reference group not involved in the survey, can help clarify what information you have and what is missing. *Finding a unifying and specific vision for a complex landscape is hard. Identifying multiple points of common interest and a broad target like 'livable countryside' can serve as a more realistic starting point for moving forward.*

Building blocks for strategies

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Figure 3: A depiction of the building blocks that can inform strategies and which should be collectively explored.

Third phase: Articulating and describing strategies

Based on the acquired understanding of what the building blocks (ingredients) for different strategies might be and what the strategies aim to achieve, the main task in Phase 3 is to engage with stakeholders to start discussing recipes, that is, jointly exploring how available options may be combined for taking (collective) action and thinking through strategies for navigating change and, if need be, transform the system. Guiding questions are *'What are the different ways to reach a desired future?', 'What actions should be taken, by whom, where, at what level and when?', 'What are existing or potential barriers to taking action?' and 'What are direct and indirect outcomes of taking action?'*

- **Methods**

Phase 3 may, for example, use a combination of the online survey described under Phase 2 and a more active deliberation process (webinars, workshops, focus groups, or combinations of them).

At the center of the workshops and webinars are small group exercises and tasks where people discuss their preferences, understanding of key components and how they could be combined into strategies. However, the group work can be complemented with individual exercises in cases where it is important to avoid influence by others and capture the full range of contrasting experiences and opinions as well as consensus.

- **Critical factors and reflection points**

Start with already existing strategies or the actions participants can see themselves engaging in. Starting with something more 'concrete' may actually help people to reflect and think beyond their current reality. One way can be to ask participants to describe inspirational examples, in their own area or elsewhere, which they see as opportunities for change. **Designing and planning exercises together with key stakeholders and local partners** may help facilitate the process.

Strategies may be conceived as:

- i. Parallel, co-occurring alternative land uses in the landscape, for example strategies for maintaining open lands and for sustainable forestry,
- ii. Alternative management strategies for each land use, for example forestry strategies focusing on certification or a shift from pines and spruces to deciduous trees and other forms of income diversification, and
- iii. Transversal strategies that may influence conditions for all other strategies, for example strategies contribution to rural livability and viability (Figure 4).

Landscape management based on inclusive conservation

Figure 4: Graphical representation of parallel land use strategies in the landscape, alternative strategies for each land use, and strategies that are cross-sectional, all of which may contribute to inclusive conservation of cultural landscapes.

Fourth phase: Connecting strategies

At this stage we have a list of interconnected actors and actions that target different goals, and that are connected to a specific agency and opportunity context. Moving forward from this description of individual strategies (alternative management strategies as well as supporting strategies), the final step is to build a better understanding of how strategies interact and could together work as a dynamic, flexible 'inclusive landscape strategy'. Using the same components - actors, actions, barriers to action and outcomes of actions - strategies can be connected in four different ways (Figure 5):

1. Actors may be involved in multiple strategies, forming a natural bridge but also a vulnerability (the exit of an actor would affect not only one strategy);
2. Different strategies may involve the same or similar action points that could be coordinated even if the overall strategies are different otherwise;
3. Strategies may be hampered by the same barriers, similar to the action points;
4. Outcomes of one strategy may create or remove barriers for other strategies.

Apart from connections between strategies, a specific strategy might also be more or less flexible; some strategies may become static lock-ins only concerned with preserving status quo while others transform and change as they move forward. Once you have identified existing and potential strategies and filtered your actions for feasibility and effectiveness, the last step is to consider when and why you may want to consider switching between strategies and what the consequences might be. You may have discussed the strategies based on current conditions or with a particular future in mind. However, testing and discussing also less likely futures will help you both anticipate change and identify and reflect on trends and their possible implications.

- **Methods**

Depending on the outcomes of Phases 1-3, Phase 4 may include webinars and workshops, modelling, or participatory scenario analyses.

Workshop exercises can include mapping strategies and their different interconnections, identification of situations when changing or revising strategies would be needed, discussing strategies relative to different uncertainties and future scenarios, or linking proposed measures to a diagram of relevant actors to anticipate responses.

- **Critical factors and reflection points**

For the continued strategizing it is important to consider **how to create the most powerful combination of the minimum number of actions, and how different actions should be sequenced in time and coordinated across scales.** At this stage the deliberation process may need to shift towards a more long term continuous process with recurring meetings. This may include changing roles and encouraging stakeholders to claim ownership and take lead. For this to be a smooth transition it needs to be addressed already in the first phases of the project.

Figure 5: Interdependencies of coexisting or alternative strategies need to be explored and understood to find synergies and tradeoffs among them.

Take home learnings from the Västra Harg pilot case for designing a process

- **Building relations is key, but how do you do this when physical meetings are at a minimum?**

Small things matter, like sending individual emails to people adapted to them and their work, finding opportunities to meet in person or join external events organized by the participants of your process. **Remind participants that their specific perspective matters to the process.** Soft skills like active listening and having an open attitude help. Critical decisions to be discussed with stakeholders during a pandemic are whether it makes sense to go along with planned activities in a digital format, or postpone until physical meetings become safe.

- **Navigating the uncertainty of the learning process.**

An explorative, deliberative learning process means that you do not know beforehand exactly what the focal points will be – **the framing and discussion points develop over the course of the project.** Communicate as clearly as you can what the boundaries are - objectives, mandate, resources etc. and discuss what can be done within these frames to best meet participant interests.

- **Anchor the project in collaborations with local and regional partners.**

Especially if you are an 'external' actor, finding local partners with a shared interest, and who are willing to invest some time, is invaluable. It makes the process more locally relevant and increases the chances that project outcomes will live on after the project. **For a fruitful collaboration it is important to clarify expectations on roles and outcomes early on and formulate a clear intent with the process that meets both your own and the partner's interests.** The approach described here has a specific objective - identifying, describing and connecting different strategies that could contribute to inclusive conservation - and this has to be made clear.

- **Accommodating a broad group of stakeholders with different opportunities to participate.**

This is a challenge throughout a deliberation process as participants differ in their preferences for how to collaborate, in the perceived importance given to different issues and the practical circumstances of their involvement (e.g. professionally or privately). These differences make it difficult (or impossible) to find a format, time, topic and language that suits everyone. A recommendation is to run at least part of the process in parallel focus groups in order to be able to go deeper into certain topics that might not be relevant for the whole group.

- **The workshops and, even more so, webinars must be carefully designed and facilitated.**

It is challenging to make everyone in a diverse group feel welcome and included. Also, clear protocols for data management and sharing are required, and group dynamics and potential disagreements need to be handled. Hence, it is essential for a successful process that the core team has competence and experience in process design, facilitation and communication, and that these different roles are divided among the core team members.

- **Plan for several iterations.**

More iterations allow for better validation, more opportunities to triangulate and to dig deeper into issues. Each phase offers opportunities for several iterations, as time and stakeholder interests allow. This was built into our Delphi inspired survey design, but also into the webinar and workshop set-up with the follow-up webinar afterwards where participants can feed back on preliminary results. In this way, the Västtra Harg process sustained a multi-fora dialogue between research and practice.

- **Trust the process.**

Planning an effective collaborative process in a multifunctional landscape is challenging. But when done well, it has enormous potential to build capacity among stakeholders to collaborate, be better positioned to anticipate change, take transformative actions, and ultimately ensure that both people and biodiversity can continue to flourish.

References

1. IPBES (2019). Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3553579>
2. Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (2020). Global Biodiversity Outlook 5 – Summary for Policy Makers. Montréal. Online URL: <https://www.cbd.int/gbo5>
3. European Commission (2020). EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 - Bringing nature back into our lives. COM(2020)380.
4. Folke, C., Carpenter, S. R., Walker, B., Scheffer, M., Chapin, T., and Rockström, J. (2010). Resilience thinking: integrating resilience, adaptability and transformability. *Ecology and Society* 15(4): 20. <http://www.ecologyandsociety.org/vol15/iss4/art20/>
5. Enfors-Kautsky, E., Järnberg, L., Quinlan, A., and Ryan, P. (2018). Wayfinder: a resilience guide for navigating towards sustainable futures. GRAID programme, Stockholm Resilience Center. Online URL: www.wayfinder.earth
6. Stockholm Resilience Centre (2016). Applying resilience thinking. Seven principles for building resilience in social-ecological systems. Online URL: http://applyingresilience.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2016/04/Applying_resilience_thinking.pdf
7. Resilience Alliance (2010). Assessing resilience in social-ecological systems: Workbook for practitioners. Version 2.0. Online URL: <https://www.resalliance.org/resilience-assessment>
8. Lade, S. J., Walker, B.H., and Haider, L. J. (2020). Resilience as pathway diversity: linking systems, individual, and temporal perspectives on resilience. *Ecology and Society* 25(3):19. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-11760-250319>
9. Länsstyrelsen Östergötland (2020). Västra Hargs lövskogar naturreservat. Online URL: <https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/ostergotland/besoksmal/naturreservat/vastra-hargs-lovskogar-naturreservat.html>, accessed 2020-12-08
10. Länsstyrelsen Östergötland (2015). Bevarandeplan för Natura 2000-området Västra Harg 0230324
11. ENVISION (2020). Fact Sheet: ENVISION: promoting inclusive conservation in protected areas - From a shared understanding of problems and solutions toward resilient landscape strategies for Västra Hargs Lövskogar nature reserve and its surrounding cultural landscape in Mjölby Municipality (Sweden). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4304053](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4304053)
12. ENVISION (2020). Policy Brief: Towards an Inclusive Global Biodiversity Framework. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4304086](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4304086)

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For more information

Erik Andersson, Associate professor,
Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University

✉ erik.andersson@su.se

🖱 inclusive-conservation.org

🐦 [@Envision2050](https://twitter.com/Envision2050)

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